

SUBJECTIVE PERCEPTION OF DISCHARGE FROM THE HOSPITAL BY ELDERLY PATIENTS WITH MENTAL DISORDERS WITH SIGNS OF HOSPITALIZATION

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Abstract. *One of the most important conditions for the successful adaptation, social activity and self-awareness of individuals with mental disorders is their psychological well-being. The presence of chronic mental illness should not be taken as a basis for unconditional disability, and the fact that at this stage of medical development it is incurable does not mean that it is necessary to help such a person, make his life comfortable and meaningful, form his positive self-attitude and not force him to hide or replace the fact of the disease.*

Key words: *mental illness, elderly patient, social activity, disability.*

СУБЪЕКТИВНОЕ ВОСПРИЯТИЕ ВЫПИСКИ ИЗ БОЛЬНИЦЫ ПОЖИЛЫМИ ПАЦИЕНТАМИ С ПСИХИЧЕСКИМИ НАРУШЕНИЯМИ С ПРИЗНАКАМИ ГОСПИТАЛИЗАЦИИ

Аннотация. *Одним из важнейших условий успешной адаптации, социальной активности и самосознания лиц с психическими расстройствами является их психологическое благополучие. Наличие хронического психического заболевания не следует принимать за основание безусловной инвалидности, а то, что на данном этапе развития медицины оно неизлечимо, не означает, что необходимо помочь такому человеку, сделать его жизнь комфортной и осмысленной. формировать у него положительное самоотношение, а не заставлять его скрывать или заменять факт заболевания.*

Ключевые слова: *психическое заболевание, пожилой пациент, социальная активность, инвалидность.*

Introduction. The possibility of obtaining psychiatric help in a timely and high-quality manner is not only the key to the patient's personal well-being, but is also very important socially, as it reduces the likelihood of inappropriate and potentially dangerous behaviors for individuals with mental illness themselves and those around them [1-3]. At the same time, the importance of social predictors in the formation of the field of human health often exceeds the importance of pure clinical parameters [4]. At the same time, in modern society, the problem of tolerance towards the category of citizens with mental disabilities is very relevant – they are not only undesirable as colleagues, acquaintances or neighbors, but are also sources of potential danger [5].

With the great social resonance of the circumstances in which particularly cruel, destructive crimes were committed, the ambiguous, often contradictory attitude of society towards the individuals who committed them attracts attention. A part of the population, even before a special examination is carried out, evaluates them as mentally retarded, while others strongly defend the position of unconditional responsibility of such subjects to the law, ignoring possible medical aspects. Experts know that aggressive actions that are funny on the outside and that are specific or less motivated can be carried out both by the mentally ill and by individuals who do not have mental illness. However, simple judgments that often dominate the minds of people, shape public opinion [6-9].

The expectation of social behavior of people with mental disorders, as predicted by society, indirectly affects the perception of their own personality and self-attitude of such people. The pressure of the position formed by the media makes it difficult for psychiatrists and psychologists to carry out forensic examinations, carry out treatment for persons deemed insane by the court and cancel medical measures [10-12].

In connection with the above, the formation of awareness by the mentally ill about the presence of chronic mental illness in the implementation of mandatory treatment and observation in inpatient and outpatient conditions, and at the same time the presence of a sufficient and positive self-attitude with self-acceptance, as well as the restoration or absorption of successful [13-15].

This problem is very relevant in general psychiatric practice. Researchers emphasize the feasibility of implementing psycho-educational programs that provide information and socio-psychological assistance to both the patient himself and his family, allow the patient with the necessary knowledge that affects his attitude and behavior towards his health, as well as establish cooperative relationships with doctors [16-18]. The authors prove the effectiveness of the integrated model of the program, which combines the information module with interpersonal communication training and behavioral therapy [19].

A significant positive effect of the formation of psychosis against the background of active psychocorrection affects the increase in the constructiveness of coping strategy patients [20]. L. A. Karaseva et al. emphasize the importance of conducting rehabilitation and expert diagnostics for the development of an individual complex of rehabilitation measures. At the same time, pathopsychological studies are considered as an important structural link in such programs that allow you to objectify mental disorder, the social and psychological state of the patient, assess the resilience and severity of mental activity disorders [21-24].

At the same time, the importance of social support and partnership in the implementation of rehabilitation and Correctional activities, the importance of extramarital forms of work, the prospects for interaction between the patient, doctor and representatives of the public organization (specific volunteers) in the process of patient re-adaptation are noted [25-27].

Taking into account the positive dynamics of the prevention indicators of socially dangerous behavior (OOD) in the mentally ill, there are two trends at once: on the one hand, the combination of compulsory treatment with general psychiatric practice, on the other – its further specialization. Given this, we can say that the socio-psychological components in mandatory treatment are similar to the general clinic, but often more specific and their spectrum is wider [28].

Mandatory psychiatric treatment should be considered in a wide social and time continuity – psychiatric (psychological) Anamnesis and features of the patient's vital activity before committing an offense, specific features and mechanisms of a criminal offense, stationization after passing an examination to a psychiatric institution and prospects for re-adaptation after changing or stopping medical measures. This is the only process that consists of certain stages, but they are not discrete [29-31]. The success of the drug effect, including the use of more effective drugs of the new generation, the reduction of symptoms due to correction and psychotherapy, and positive neoplasms are the basis for a meaningful and semantic transition to the next stage at each stage. In the process of treatment, regardless of its stages, it is necessary to proceed from a general strategy and goal in the interaction of all doctors, psychologists, social workers, secondary health workers and others involved in the process. The most important condition for the effectiveness of treatment is the complexity of the approach with the individuality of the program and the instructions-the duration of positive consequences, the reduction of the risk of recurrence of illegal behavior, the inclusion of the patient in a complex system of social relations after discharge [32-35].

The implementation of such a strategy determines the constant growth of the role of a psychologist and the complexity of his professional tasks. It not only analyzes the characteristics of the intellectual activity and voluntary sphere of the patient at each stage of mandatory treatment,

but also provides a focused study of the motivational-value system of the patient, his communicative resources and methods, the specifics and effectiveness of protective mechanisms. In the context of compulsory treatment, these characteristics can be fully determined not only during a pathopsychological experiment using methods, but also during the patient's behavior in the department, the process of interaction with other patients, during occupational therapy, as well as during psychocorrectional conversations and activities, obtaining important information [36].

Changes in the system of value orientations, attitudes towards oneself, existing illness, personal meanings associated with the environment require complex internal work from the patient and certain intellectual and personal resources. At the same time, the state of forced isolation and restrictions, on the one hand, is an external stimulus for some patients, an impetus for self-reflection [37]. On the other hand, events that are mostly negative experiences, often contrary to positive self-attitudes and often self-esteem, are analyzed, which can be accompanied by negative color experiences [38]. Perhaps the most difficult thing to accept is not the fact that an offense was committed by the patient, but the presence of his chronic mental illness. Therefore, it is easier for many patients to refuse to work on themselves, especially since the main responsibility for what is happening is almost automatically staying in a psychiatric hospital owned by the doctor (which is necessary and natural during the period of cessation of acute psychotic symptoms) helps to occupy a passive position [39]. At the same time, patients strive to replace or rationalize what happened (acute painful experiences, OOD), ignore the disease and look for psychologically understandable, reliable explanations. In the case of a serious offense, patients pay attention to the pain of their condition during an offense, but still interpret it as temporary [40].

Taking such a position is facilitated indirectly by stereotypes of the attitude towards the mentally ill existing in society, the lack of tolerance towards chronic mental disorders and their consequences. At the same time, many patients of mental hospitals and their relatives unconsciously in the internal plan, the subjective rejection of the disease turns into dissatisfaction with the quality of medicine, doctors and services provided. In the minds of the population, certain manifestations of the disease are seen as a sign of weakness, self-control, "lack of self-control" or inability to make a balanced decision [41]. Waiting for the rapid effect of taking medications (such "ideas" are discussed in the media, popular talk shows, expressed by authorized persons), as the patient progresses to full adequacy, personal and intellectual wealth, characteristic of a large part of the population, largely determines the position of the patient who enters treatment. In addition, this also applies to individuals who have experienced mental activity disorders for the first time and have been placed in psychiatric hospitals (PBS) many times [42].

Often, relatives of patients who are focused on Compulsory Treatment see this as a temporary solution to a personal social problem – isolation of inadequate and often aggressive behavior of the family. At the same time, they attach the greatest importance to the important, but not the main reasons for the social adaptation of their relatives – alcoholism, drug addiction, dysfunctional environment or the patient's behavior as a result of dirt and laziness. The fact of chronic mental illness is replaced, ignored, rejected or recognized as a temporary phenomenon [43].

These trends are certainly destabilizing factors for a person undergoing mandatory treatment. A psychiatrist and psychologist require additional efforts to overcome not only the internal resistance of the patient, but also the position of his social environment [44].

Analysis of dynamic diagnostic and corrective work carried out by psychologists with patients undergoing inpatient psychiatric mandatory treatment in a general type hospital shows the seriousness and importance of socio-psychological problems on this continent [45]. Part of these problems are internal in nature, since it is caused or indirectly related to the mental illness present in the patient. Other difficulties arise for objective reasons, which cannot be practically solved by the efforts of the employees of the department, therefore, the psychologist is tasked with forming a certain attitude and a different attitude towards himself and life circumstances in the patient [46].

At each stage of compulsory treatment in a psychiatric hospital, the meaningful and semantic effect on the patient has a certain orientation. First, it is necessary to place the patient in a closed institution, to cope with the effects of stress caused by limiting his freedom and social circle [47]. At the same time, it is necessary to take into account the ambiguous attitude of this contingent towards the expert decision and its consequences: some patients believe that it is more convenient to be in the hospital, and not in places of imprisonment, regardless of the presence of the disease; others claim to have a conditional or minimal term and prefer to avoid the "social stamp" of the mentally ill in any case. When primary adaptation to conditions of being in a closed psychiatric ward is achieved, treatment requires attitude formation and cognitive full awareness of the existence of psychopathological experiences that lead to mental illness and related behavioral disorders and illicit behaviors [48].

The formation of such an attitude in people with acute psychopathological symptoms, gross disorders of adaptation requires a relatively long time and mobilization of all personal resources, and is possible only after and against the background of drug therapy. In improving the mental and psychological state in the rehabilitation process, it is important to introduce measures and methods

of psychocorrection aimed at indirectly, gradually introducing the patient to work on his future [49].

This includes not only understanding the peculiarities of the disease present for the patient and its manifestations, social problems associated with him, but also planning the future, taking into account the specific situation in which the subject appears after discharge, his surroundings, real professional skills and opportunities, potential risks. (for example, alcoholism or typical conflicts) [50].

The purpose of this study was to investigate the subjective assessment of the results of inpatient treatment and the reaction to the discharge of patients with mental disorders and symptoms of hospitalization.

Materials and methods. The sample consisted of 122 patients aged 55 to 91 (median age $67,37 \pm 7,8$ years) admitted to the SOPB unit from January 2021 to January 2023, of whom 104 were women (85,2%) and 18 were men (14,8%). 39,3% of patients with recurrent depressive disorder, 20,5% of patients with depressive episodes, 19% of organic brain disorders, 1% of schizophrenia and schizotypal disorder, and 14% of neurotic and stress-related disorders.

Fifty-nine patients were separated from the total pool of those examined and identified signs of hospitalism, which formed the main group. 63 of those examined found no signs of hospitalization and entered the control group. The main and control groups did not have reliable differences in age, gender, basic diagnosis, etiology of the disease, total duration of the disease, comorbidity index.

The examination was carried out after completing the main course of treatment at the preparatory stage of discharge in the form of a semi-structured interview, which includes general socio-demographic and anamnestic data, questions about marital status, attitude to the disease, the treatment process, the effectiveness and tolerance of therapy. Correlation analysis was carried out, parametric statistical methods (student's t-criteria) were used to analyze quantitative variables, and Mann – Whitney criteria for qualitative characteristics.

Research results. During the semi-structured interview, all patients were offered an assessment on a four –point scale (emotions 1 are very strong, 4 – No), what emotions they experience in relation to the upcoming discharge and how ready they are for this event.

It has been found that patients with signs of hospitalization were more exposed to reactions such as fear (primary $3,41 \pm 0,825$; control $3,91 \pm 0,292$), excitement (primary $2,9 \pm 0,976$; control $3,48 \pm 0,566$), feeling of weakness (primary $3,17 \pm 1,085$; control $3,70 \pm 0,637$) compared to the control group.), these patients were less satisfied (basic $2,66 \pm 1,111$; control $1,94 \pm 0,864$) and

cheerful (basic $3,45 \pm 0,736$; control $2,73 \pm 0,911$), $p < 0,05$. Correlation analysis showed significant positive correlations between anxiety spectrum sensations in hospitalized patients, fear of reuptake (Pearson correlation coefficient $0,536$, $p < 0,05$), and lack of information on how new exacerbations can be prevented (Pearson correlation coefficient $0,643$, $p < 0,05$), and feelings of weakness and inability to change in these patients with side effects of therapy (Pearson correlation coefficient $0,530$, $p < 0,05$)

Subjective preparation for discharge (0 – fully ready, 2 – not ready at all) was significantly greater in the control group- $0,4 \pm 0,645$ (basic $0,79 \pm 0,658$, $p < 0,05$).

Patients in the control group reported more accurate dynamics in their cases – $67,04 \pm 23,275$ percent compared to the original case ($42,50 \pm 26,975$, $p < 0,05$ in the main group). At the same time, as a result of the correlation analysis conducted, a significant correlation between the readiness for discharge and the results of treatment was determined only in the group of hospitalized patients (Pearson correlation coefficient $0,449$, $p < 0,05$). In addition, the low level of psychological readiness for discharge in patients of the main group was associated with a familiar attitude to the hospital environment (Pearson correlation coefficient $0,643$, $p < 0,05$), high probability, subjective assessment, reuptake (Pearson correlation coefficient $0,461$, $p < 0,05$), the presence of side effects of drugs (Pearson correlation coefficient $0,461$, $p < 0,05$). Pearson correlation coefficient $0,420$ $p < 0,05$), installation in suggestive treatments (Pearson correlation coefficient $0,623$, $p < 0,05$, not having sufficient information about the nature of the disease and methods of treatment (Pearson correlation coefficient $0,751$, $p < 0,05$).

In patients in the control group, low readiness for discharge was associated with frequent intake of drugs during the day (Pearson correlation coefficient $0,421$, $p < 0,05$), the presence of side effects of therapy (Pearson correlation coefficient $0,540$, $p < 0,05$) and the tendency to associate the development of the disease with external factors (Pearson correlation coefficient $0,745$, $p < 0,05$).

Conclusions. Discharge from the hospital after the end of treatment often causes negative emotions in elderly patients, since this is due to the need to leave the relatively simple and safe environment of the hospital, fear of recurrence of the disease (Trifonov E. G., 1999, Karvasarsky B. D., 2004). In patients with signs of hospitalization, emotional reactions of the anxiety spectrum are more pronounced, and the psychological readiness for discharge is lower than in patients in the control group. In patients in the main and control group, the degree of readiness for ejaculation was determined by various factors, the common point was the presence of side effects only in prescribed drugs, but only in hospitalized patients, this factor was due to its weakness and the feeling of inability to affect the situation.

The attitude towards discharge in patients with signs of hospitalization is associated with many factors, including the perception of the situation in the hospital, lack of information about the disease and fear of relapse, dissatisfaction with the results of treatment, and non-hospitalized patients. more attention was paid to the formal assessment of the effectiveness and tolerability of therapy, and less adjusted for release if environmental factors were perceived as causing exacerbation.

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